

BENDING FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF SMART GLASS-FIBER REINFORCED VINYLESTER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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1. General Introduction

In recent years, glass-fiber reinforced composite materials are more and more used in structural applications. Their mechanical properties: low density, high strength and high chemical corrosion-resistance offer an interesting alternative solution to metallic or concrete material. The pultrusion is a composite material processing technique that is penetrating the civil engineering market since the beginning of the 90's. It is a continuous process well adapted to mass production of linearly shaped profiles. Moreover, many research on the use of pultruded structural shapes for civil engineering building and bridge applications have shown the undeniable potential for the use of these products (Bakis et al., 2002).

The studies on the reliability of civil engineering composites structures depending on damage tolerance are very important. Most of these structures should withstand a high number of cycles at elevated stress values, under various environmental conditions. The mechanical behavior of composite materials subjected to cycling loading is complex. Static and fatigue failure in pultruded composite materials exhibit different damage mechanisms such like matrix cracking, fiber-matrix debonding and fiber fractures. Performing fatigue testing, metallographic observation, as well analytical modelling are therefore essential to detect the onset of damage and to predict the sequences of damage development as a function of the applied stress.

In this contribution, the mechanical behavior of smart composite specimens under quasi-static and dynamic fatigue in 3-points bending is investigated experimentally. Acoustic emission technique is used

to detect damage development and its propagation as a function of applied stress. Embedded optical fiber-based sensors are used for strain monitoring.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials, test specimens and methods

The material under study is a pultruded composite material made with continuous glass fiber reinforcements and a vinylester resin as matrix. The fiber volume fraction is 66%.

Test specimens were manufactured from rectangular - shape profiles (dimensions : 16mm x 40mm). They were diamond saw cut and the dimensions of the specimens were 3mm x 15mm x 100mm and 320mmx40mmx16mm. These dimensions follow the recommendations of the standards: EN ISO 178. A servo-hydraulic testing machine characterized by a maximum loading capacity of 100 kN was used to perform the static and dynamic tests in three points bending, with a span-to-depth ratio of 20.

2.2 Experimental program

First, quasi-static bending tests until rupture were performed. Acoustic emission technique was also used to detect the first damage mechanisms and to monitor their evolution. The hydraulic actuator was electronically controlled in order to perform constant velocity tests at 1 mm/min. Next, fatigue tests were carried out at various different initial stress levels. The fatigue cycle was a constant amplitude triangular waveform with a frequency of 2 and 10Hz. The minimum to maximum stress ratio, R , was fixed at 0.05. Fatigue tests were run up to 2 million cycles at room temperature.

3. Results

3.1 Quasi-static 3-points bending tests

Fig. 1 shows the stress-strain curve in three points in

quasi-static bending tests, until rupture. The flexural Young modulus is about 41 GPa.

Figure 1 : Stress-strain curve under 3-point bending, coupled to acoustic emission records.

3.2. Modes of damage

The specimens in polymer matrix composite materials and continuous fiber subjected to 3-points bending behave in a very particular way (Figure 1).

Figure 2 : Evolution of acoustic emission during load-unload flexural test

The analysis of this curve, coupled with various microscopic observations, leads us to propose the following scenario that seems most likely to describe the extension of damage. The damage starts at low stress level (75 MPa) and consists of the stretching of fibers in tension (Generally, in a material obtained by pultrusion, the fibers are not aligned very straight). The same value of initiating damage is also found on the loading-unloading curve (Figure 2). Beyond this threshold, fiber-matrix debonding and matrix microcracking, parallel and transversely to the

fibers, are responsible for AE activity. Given a fiber volume fraction very high and a lower rigidity of the matrix, the matrix cracking in these materials does not cause pronounced nonlinear mechanical behavior. Under these conditions, almost to near the limit of proportionality, the cracking of the matrix along the fibers (following the fiber-matrix debonding) and transverse cracking are a priori the major damage mechanisms responsible for acoustic activity. Obviously, there must be secondary sources of EA, in particular the failure of weakest fibers.

Figure 3 : Stress-strain curve under 3-point bending plotted along with acoustic emission event amplitude

The scenario seems confirmed by the results of Figure 3, which highlights the presence of a major damage mechanism that is attributed to different types of matrix ruptures (breaks longitudinal and transverse to fibers), whose amplitude is between 35 and 45dB. With increasing strain, the fibers begin to break. This can be found on the loading curve by the output of proportionality. Beyond the yield strength, the number of broken fibers becomes important and the occurrence of the peak load reflects the almost total breakdown of the fibers on the face in traction. Beyond the maximum stress, cracking proceeds by mode II along the fiber. The multiplicity of sources, EA is clear in Figure 3, where we observe large spectrum amplitude, up to 95dB.

As a summary, the following 4 proposed sequences of damage allow a clear view of the

mechanical behavior of the material. Each is dominated by a given damage mechanism :

- The first phase starts at the beginning of the trial and ends at the registration constraint of the first acoustic emission events. This part is in principle free from damage. (= 0.22%) and the end of proportionality.
- The second phase, located between early damage. This phase shows multiple matrix damage, along with the failure of weakest fibers.
- The third phase begins at the end of proportionality and ends at the maximum stress. It is characterized by progressive failure of fibers in large numbers. The purpose of this part is reached when a critical number of fibers failures at the peak load.
- The final phase consists of an increase in mode II cracking.

The sequences depicted above are useful in the sense that they allow a direct relationship between the mechanical behavior and the evolution of the microstructure (Drissi-Habti, 1995).

3.2 Quasi-static and cyclic fatigue tests

Fig.4. Evolution of the flexural Young modulus

Quasi-static tests were carried out to get an accurate idea about the sequences of damage exhibited by the

composite. These tests enabled also the right definition of the area over which the fatigue behaviour will be investigated. Typically, fatigue test values were chosen within the area extending between the stress corresponding to the onset of damage and the end of proportionality. This choice will allow us to understand the fatigue behavior of the material to stress values that generate small differences in behavior of elasticity.

The fatigue performance in 3-points bending of the test specimens is shown in Fig. 4. Typically, there is fairly no decrease of stiffness for stresses below 186MPa, over 2 millions cycles. This is coherent with quasi-static loading tests where matrix cracking only was recorded as damage mechanism. A slight decrease is recorded for 220MPa, especially at the end of the test. This can be explained by the beginning of fiber failures. For higher stress values, a sharp decrease is recorded and can be explained by a large number of broken fibers.

The curve of the maximum flexural stress versus fatigue life (S–N) diagram is typical of FRP material (Kim et al., 1981; Lene, 1986) and it may be expressed as $\sigma_{max} = A + B \log(N)$ where, A and B are constants.

4. Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) results

Optical fiber sensors were used at various step levels:

Figure 5 : Optical fiber's signals before and after embedding into a pultruded composite profile.

- During pultrusion, to check whether optical fibers were successfully pultruded within composite profiles. One should keep in mind that not only optical fibers are introduced, but also the associated connections. The over-thickness that derives can be significantly hindered during

pultrusion. Therefore, using an optical backscattering reflectometer (OBR), broken optical fibers can easily be detected. Figure 5 shows the signals before and after embedment of an optical fiber into a pultruded profile that show that the optical sensor has not experienced any damage and was positively inserted.

On the reverse, when an optical fiber is broken, the OBR is a perfect indicator (Figure 6), where the failure of the optical fiber is clearly shown.

Figure 6 : OBR tracking showing the failure of an optical fiber embedded within a pultruded composite.

Embedded Fiber-Bragg Gratings (FBG) were used to get the deformation triggered during quasi-static flexure loading, as well. These kind of sensors have been introduced in details in previous works (Chapeleau et al., 2009). Figure 7 shows FBG standard amplitude as a function of the wavelength. This result shows clearly that there is an increase of the wavelength (thus the strain) when increasing the load.

Figure 7 : Standard amplitude of FBG as a function of the wavelength.

Figure 8 shows the strain recorded by both FBG and mechanical testing machine. To enable an easy comparison between the two signals, a lag phase was introduced. As shown on the Figure, the strain measured using FBG is smaller than the one displayed by the mechanical testing machine. This is simply the result of the difference between the strain measured by the mechanical testing machine at the extreme of the area under tension and the position of the optical fiber inserted into the heart of the area under tension, but closer to the neutral axis.

Figure 8 : Comparison of strain values delivered by FBG and the mechanical testing machine.

To get a match between the 2 signals, it is of a prime importance to run some additional mechanical calculation that help to figure out the accurate position of the FBG.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, experimental results of quasi-static and fatigue 3-point bending are presented for a composite material made with a high ratio volume of fiber.

Quasi-static tests, conducted along with acoustic emission records enabled the identification of damage mechanisms acting with increasing stress values. The definition of the stress range over which fatigue tests will be conducted was also identified.

Results of fatigue tests showed that up to 186MPa, there is fairly no stiffness reduction. Beyond this stress, fibers failures take place and therefore significant decrease of mechanical properties was recorded.

Optical fiber-based sensors were used at two step levels : At first, during pultrusion to check whether

optical fibers were successfully inserted with composite profiles. FBG were also used to monitor strain during quasi-static and fatigue loading. For both cases, the results obtained were promising.

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